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“EDUCATING THE PEOPLE ON THE CONCEPT OF MISGENDERING”

A recent issue involving the misgendering of Miss Awra Briguela has caused a stir among many Filipinos today. Miss Awra Briguela, a celebrity and social media influencer, posted on her social media account her recent achievement of graduating from Senior High School. This has gained praise from many and criticism from others, especially individuals who have conservative views on gender identity, because, as a transwoman, she used the pronoun her to identify herself in her post (Mallorca, 2025). Critics are saying that transwomen are not women but men and should use the pronoun he and him.

Awra Briguela is experiencing misgendering. It is defined as an intentional or unintentional act of using the wrong name, pronoun, or gendered language to refer to someone, which can have harmful impacts on trans people’s mental health (Jacobsen et.al, 2023). Even though the Philippines has been considered one of the most LGBT affirming nations in Asia still gender and sexual minorities still experience harm and shaming. Misgendering is a reminder that their gender identity is still not affirmed, accepted, or even tolerated in society.

The issue faced by Miss Briguela is an opportunity to educate Filipinos about concepts such as gender identity and misgendering. Affirming the right pronoun is not about being woke or political correctness but respecting and appreciating the diversity of individuals. It is about affirming human dignity and being a role model to others, especially to the younger generation, that we can be respectful of one another even if we have differences.

In our society today, showing compassion and understanding is important. We are challenged to avoid misgendering and be respectful of people’s gender identity. Through dialogue, educational awareness, and respecting each other’s pronouns, we can create a more inclusive and just world for all.

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